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Tutoring as a new model of pedagogical mentoring

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Abstract. The aim of the article is to theoretically substantiate the essence of tutoring and tutor support as an innovative pedagogical technology and a special form of mentoring in the modern education system. To analyze their potential in ensuring individualization of learning, development of students' personal potential and construction of individual educational trajectories, in particular in the conditions of primary school.

The study used a complex of general scientific and special pedagogical methods: theoretical analysis and synthesis of scientific sources, comparative and historical method, systematization and generalization of scientific approaches, interpretation of domestic and foreign concepts of tutoring.

The categories of “tutor”, “tutoring”, “tutoring activity” and “tutoring support” are analyzed on the basis of modern scientific sources. It is determined that tutoring is not only a pedagogical technology, but also a special culture of subject-subject interaction aimed at supporting self-knowledge, self-determination and self-realization of the student. The differences between pedagogical support and tutoring support are clarified, in particular, it is emphasized that tutoring support focuses on the individual educational trajectory and internal resources of the individual. The main functions and roles of the tutor are revealed, the stages and components of tutoring activity that provide holistic support for learning are outlined. The specifics of tutoring in primary school as a space for the development of motivation, cognitive interests and independence of students are shown.

Tutoring and tutoring support are effective tools for modernizing the educational process, ensuring the personalization of learning, the formation of internal motivation and the ability to learn throughout life. Therefore, tutoring should be considered as a strategic direction for the development of modern schools in the context of the transition to individualized and competency-based education.

Keywords: *tutoring; tutor; tutoring activity; tutor support; individual educational trajectory; individualization of learning; primary education; mentoring; personalized learning; educational development.*

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Анотація. Метою статті є теоретичне обґрунтування сутності тьюторингу та тьюторського супроводу як інноваційної педагогічної технології й особливої форми наставництва в системі сучасної освіти, а також аналіз їхнього потенціалу в забезпеченні індивідуалізації навчання, розвитку особистісного потенціалу здобувачів освіти та побудови індивідуальних освітніх траєкторій, зокрема в умовах початкової школи.

У дослідженні використано комплекс загальнонаукових і спеціально-педагогічних методів: теоретичний аналіз і синтез наукових джерел, порівняльно-історичний метод, систематизацію та узагальнення наукових підходів, інтерпретацію вітчизняних і зарубіжних концепцій тьюторства.

У статті здійснено ґрунтовний аналіз категорій «тьютор», «тьюторство», «тьюторська діяльність» і «тьюторський супровід» на основі сучасних наукових джерел. Визначено, що тьюторинг є не лише педагогічною технологією, а й особливою культурою суб'єкт-суб'єктної взаємодії, спрямованою на підтримку самопізнання, самовизначення й самореалізації здобувача освіти. Уточнено відмінності між педагогічним і тьюторським супроводом, зокрема акцентовано, що тьюторський супровід зосереджується на індивідуальній освітній траєкторії та внутрішніх ресурсах особистості. Розкрито основні функції та ролі тьютора (наставник, консультант, керівник освітньої траєкторії, фасилітатор), окреслено етапи та компоненти тьюторської діяльності, що забезпечують цілісну підтримку навчання. Показано специфіку тьюторингу в початковій школі як простору розвитку мотивації, пізнавальних інтересів і самостійності учнів.

Тьюторинг і тьюторський супровід виступають ефективними інструментами модернізації освітнього процесу, що забезпечують персоналізацію навчання, формування внутрішньої мотивації та здатності до навчання впродовж життя. Отже, тьюторинг доцільно розглядати як стратегічний напрям розвитку сучасної школи в умовах переходу до індивідуалізованої та компетентісно орієнтованої освіти.

Ключові слова: тьюторинг; тьютор; тьюторська діяльність; тьюторський супровід; індивідуальна освітня траєкторія; індивідуалізація навчання; початкова освіта; наставництво; персоналізоване навчання; освітній розвиток.

Problem statement. Modern education operates in conditions of increasing complexity, variability and uncertainty of educational trajectories, which is due to rapid social, technological and cultural changes. The traditional model of education, oriented mainly on unified programs and frontal forms of work, increasingly less meets the needs of personally oriented, competent and inclusive education. This contradiction is especially acute in primary school, where the foundations of educational motivation, cognitive activity and the subjective position of the child are laid.

In these conditions, there is a growing need for pedagogical models that allow combining standardized educational requirements with individual needs, abilities, and pace of development of each student. That is why tutoring and tutor support are increasingly considered as promising innovative technologies that can ensure the individualization of the educational process, support for independence, reflection, and conscious educational choice. At the same time, in the Ukrainian educational space, these phenomena remain insufficiently systematized both from a theoretical and methodological point of view.

Previous research. The issue of tutoring in modern education is widely presented in the works of Ukrainian scientists and is considered in the context of

individualization of learning, partnership interaction and professional transformation of the role of the teacher. L. Bernadzikovska [1] defines tutoring as an effective method of individualization of educational trajectories, aimed at supporting the academic and personal development of students. Similarly, A. Boyko and N. Demyanenko [2] interpret tutoring as a model of partnership between a teacher and a student, based on subject-subject interaction and joint design of learning.

Scientists O. Bundak, A. Popov, Yu. Tuz [3] analyze the formation of tutoring in the Ukrainian educational space as an innovative form of pedagogical support, which is at the stage of institutionalization. S. Vetrov [5] in his works clarifies the concept of tutoring activity and proposes an algorithm for its implementation, which creates a methodological basis for practical implementation.

In the context of digitalization of education, researchers N. Garan and G. Zinchenko [7] consider tutoring support as a tool for personalizing learning in the context of the development of information and communication technologies. Scientists T. Vorontsova and V. Ponomarenko [6] connect tutoring with the formation of key competencies and life skills relevant to modern social challenges.

The problems of professional training of tutors are systematically revealed in the works of the author K. Osadchaya [13-16], who substantiates the interdisciplinary and methodological principles of the formation of tutoring competence and raises the issue of institutionalization of the tutoring profession. Scientists N. Merkulova, A. Pozdnyakova, O. Kyrylina [12] offer criteria and indicators of teachers' readiness for tutoring activities, and researcher S. Tolochko [17] emphasizes the importance of scientific and methodological competence of teachers for the implementation of tutoring practices.

However, most studies are predominantly theoretical in nature and do not sufficiently reflect empirically based models of tutoring support in higher education, its connection with the competence and socio-emotional development of students. It is

these gaps that determine the need for further research aimed at clarifying the content, mechanisms and effectiveness of tutoring activities in a modern university.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Analysis of scientific sources shows a significant number of approaches to the interpretation of the concepts of “tutor”, “tutoring”, “tutoring activity” and “tutoring support”, however, there is no consistent and holistic conceptualization of them in the context of modern school, especially primary education. In scientific works, tutoring is considered either as a pedagogical technology, or as a form of mentoring, or as a special culture of interaction, which complicates its practical implementation in the educational process.

The issues of the ratio of tutoring support to traditional pedagogical support, the specificity of the tutor's functions in primary school conditions, as well as the structure and stages of tutoring activity in working with younger schoolchildren remain insufficiently researched. A separate problem is the fragmentation of scientific models of tutoring activity, which does not always allow building a holistic system of support for the individual educational trajectory of a student. This necessitates further theoretical generalization and clarification of the content and structure of tutoring activities as an innovative pedagogical practice.

Formulation of the objectives of the research. The purpose of the article is to theoretically substantiate the essence of tutoring and tutor support as an innovative pedagogical technology and form of mentoring in modern education, as well as to determine their role in ensuring the individualization of the educational process, in particular in primary school.

Presentation of the main research material. In modern foreign scientific research of the last decade, the term “tutor” is increasingly associated with technological approaches to learning: in particular, with the use of a computer as a virtual tutor, the use of intelligent learning systems, automated tutoring programs and educational environments that are able to conduct a dialogue in natural language and model the behavior of a real tutor in an online format [1; 2; 13].

In Ukrainian scientific discourse, the concept of “tutor” is interpreted in a multifaceted way, which reflects the complexity and multidimensionality of this pedagogical role.

Tutoring is considered by many Ukrainian scientists as one of the technologies of individualized learning. Thus, S. Tolochko defines tutoring as a pedagogical activity that is combined with a particularly orderly education system [17, p. 237]. V. Kuzmin interprets tutoring as one of the institutionalized forms of mentoring, as a technology for individualizing education [9, p. 247]. A. Boyko presents the concept of “tutoring” as a form of individual work of students and teachers, aimed at developing motivation and interest in learning, activating independent personality formation. It is also important to note the researcher’s remark that tutoring technology of learning involves subject-subject interaction [2, p. 9].

Ukrainian scientists consider a tutor as an integrative pedagogical figure that combines the functions of a mentor, coordinator of individual learning, facilitator of personal development and organizer of an educational environment aimed at individualization and humanization of modern education.

In the context of our study, we will adhere to the following understanding of the concept of “tutor”: a person who, based on the clarification of the individual educational trajectory of the student's personality, ensures the development of an individual educational route and support for his individual educational program, organizing the achievement of the educational goals of the individual. A student is a subject of tutoring activity, in the context of school education – a child (a student of primary, secondary or high school).

Fundamental research in the field of tutoring is contained in the works of foreign researchers. American researcher and political figure E. Powell considers tutoring as a specific form of support provided to students in order to achieve the necessary level of mastery of basic educational skills that meets the requirements of

their class [19]. A similar position is taken by the executive director of the US Education Industry Association S. Pines, who defines tutoring as a component of the field of additional educational services. In his opinion, the main goal of tutoring is to increase the level of mastery of individual competencies, in particular in the field of mathematics, reading, writing, etc. [21].

Thus, S. Pines considers tutoring as a purposeful activity that contributes to the development and improvement of insufficiently formed learning skills of students, increasing their level of readiness for successful acquisition of quality education.

Polish researchers A. Brzezinska and L. Rycielska consider tutoring as a pedagogical practice based on the principles of an individualized approach to the student. In this context, a professor or teacher who performs the functions of a tutor is at the same time a mentor, a teacher, and an academic supervisor, and the student is not a passive listener, but an active participant in the educational process. A feature of such relationships is the presence of a trusting and partnership atmosphere between the tutor and the student, which creates favorable conditions for the intellectual and social growth of the student [20, p. 21].

Thus, in the context outlined above, academic tutoring is defined as a form of tutoring practice that aims to develop students' educational potential through personalized intellectual interaction and in-depth reflection.

E. Gordon, R. Morgan, C. O'Malley and J. Pontichello present tutoring as one of the key and necessary educational practices of our time. In their opinion, tutoring is an effective tool designed to help a wide range of children and adults maximize their personal potential in learning [16, p. 63].

For a deeper understanding of the essence of tutoring, it is extremely important to analyze the concept of tutoring support, which is its key element.

The scientific and pedagogical literature outlines various types of support, among which the following are distinguished: pedagogical; methodological;

informational; scientific and methodological; informational and methodological; consulting; tutoring [20, p. 58].

Each of these types has its own goals, functions and specifics of implementation, but they are united by a common goal - creating conditions for the holistic development of the student.

Pedagogical support and tutoring support have many common features, since both are focused on supporting the individual in the process of learning and development. In particular, pedagogical support is interpreted as a form of pedagogical activity, which includes both preventive support in the formation of the child's ability to independently plan his/her own life strategy and educational trajectory, organize his/her own activities, solve problem situations, and constant response to the child's emotional states and create conditions for overcoming emotional discomfort [6, p. 15].

Tutoring support is considered a special type of pedagogical interaction, the main goal of which is the individualization of the educational process. Support is aimed at identifying and developing the student's educational interests and internal motivations, selecting appropriate educational resources, constructing a personalized educational trajectory, as well as forming the ability to reflect on his own learning and educational needs [7, p. 66].

Tutoring is an effective response to the challenges of the transition to individualized and variable learning. It supports the implementation of the principles of lifelong learning, where the emphasis shifts from the traditional transfer of knowledge to the development of creative abilities, flexible competencies, the ability to learn independently, adapt to change, and make informed professional choices throughout life (lifelong learning) [20].

Thus, both types of support – pedagogical and tutoring – are based on the principle of individualization. At the same time, there are important differences between them: in particular, pedagogical support, along with solving educational

tasks, also includes the function of forming a student's life strategy. In contrast, tutoring support focuses mainly on the educational route, the development of internal resources and the independence of the student.

In this study, tutoring support is considered as one of the key functions of tutoring activity, which, although closely related to the concept of "tutoring", is not completely identical with it. If tutoring acts as a broader phenomenon that includes various roles and approaches to mentoring in education, then tutoring support can be defined as a specific pedagogical practice of subject-subject interaction, which involves holistic support of the individual in learning, upbringing and development.

Thus, tutoring support is a comprehensive approach aimed at individualizing the learning process through activating the internal potential of the individual. Its main goal is to create conditions for deeper self-knowledge and realization of the creative abilities of the student.

Due to the wide range of functions performed by the tutor in the process of educational interaction, scientists propose a classification of types of tutoring activity. Thus, A. Voloshina distinguishes several types of tutoring depending on the roles and tasks assigned to the tutor: tutor-mentor; tutor-consultant; tutor-manager of the educational trajectory; tutor in the field of interdisciplinary education [15, p. 80].

T. Kovaleva in her research substantiates the classification of types of tutoring depending on the educational level or the field in which tutoring activity is implemented. It distinguishes the following types: tutoring in primary school; tutoring in basic school; tutoring in high school; tutoring in the system of additional education [8].

Special attention within the framework of our study deserves tutoring activity in the field of primary education, which is one of the most flexible, variable and multifaceted. It covers not only the support of the educational process, but also a wider range of support for personal growth, development of creativity and self-

realization of the student.

In the field of primary education, several main areas of tutoring work can be distinguished:

- development of an individual educational program for a specific individual, taking into account his/her interests, abilities, motivational attitudes and educational needs within the framework of additional education programs;

- formation of the student's ability to self-help, independent choice of effective methods of learning, self-knowledge and communication, which are extremely important in the conditions of a modern information society;

- joint work on creating and maintaining an educational portfolio that records the results of personal progress, achievements and development of competencies in various areas of activity [8; 11].

In addition, the tutor can provide support to the student in preparing for participation in competitions, festivals, exhibitions, scientific competitions, where the demonstration of acquired knowledge, skills and products of activity takes place. He/she helps not only to formalize the results, but also to present them in the most advantageous format for evaluation by an expert jury or a wide audience.

In addition to providing individual support to the student, the tutor can act as an initiator and facilitator of group creative or educational projects, organize meaningful leisure, motivational trainings, intensives, master classes, etc. for students of different ages. Thus, his/her activities contribute not only to the formation of educational results, but also to the development of social skills, team interaction, leadership potential and emotional intelligence [3, p. 12].

In general, tutoring can be considered as a comprehensive, flexible, and adaptive pedagogical practice that integrates individual mentoring, educational consulting, development of personal potential, and support for students' social and communicative activity.

In the context of modern changes in the role of a teacher both in the education system and in society as a whole, there is a need for a deeper analysis of scientific approaches to determining the essence of tutoring activity. The modern transformation of the educational process in secondary education institutions requires a rethinking of the traditional pedagogical functions of the teacher, and it is in this aspect that tutoring activity acquires particular relevance and significance.

The scientific literature presents a variety of interpretations of the concept of “tutoring activity”, which reflects the ambiguous attitude of the pedagogical community to this phenomenon. Different authors focus on different aspects: some – on the methodological basis, others – on organizational functions or communicative practices. Such variability indicates that the concept of tutoring is in a state of active formation and rethinking.

In scientific research, tutoring is interpreted as a complex and multidimensional pedagogical phenomenon that combines educational, upbringing and personal development functions. In the process of analyzing a number of scientific works, we managed to identify various approaches to understanding the essence of tutoring, which reflect the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon and different scientific positions on its interpretation. Scientists understand tutoring as:

- a targeted process of pedagogical support for individualized learning, which consists in assisting the student in realizing his/her own cognitive needs, designing a trajectory of professional growth and developing self-education skills (K. Osadcha, S. Vetrov) [5; 46];
- a special form of mentoring and personalized support, which is based on subject-subject interaction, where the tutor acts as a facilitator of the student’s personal potential, relying on the best traditions of classical university education (N. Demyanenko, A. Boyko) [9];

- humanitarian practice and innovative technology aimed at forming an individual educational space of the individual, where the key task is to work with the image of the future and the student's self-determination (V. Nikitin) [14];
- coordination and mediation activities that ensure effective communication between the applicant, educational resources and the academic environment, adapting the educational opportunities of the institution to the needs of a specific individual (O. Bundak, N. Merkulova) [3; 12];
- a tool for developing subjectivity and responsible choice, where the main focus is on reflective support for the child in the process of making independent decisions regarding their own educational progress (T. Shvets) [18];
- socio-pedagogical support and adaptation technology within the inclusive space, which ensures individualization of learning for individuals with special educational needs through the creation of a specific resource environment (O. Litovka) [10].

Based on the generalization of these approaches, we concluded that tutoring activity is a holistic, systematically organized set of actions carried out at the methodological, psychological-pedagogical and methodological levels, and is aimed at supporting and accompanying the process of individualization of education. Its main goal is to develop, implement and adapt an individual educational program that meets the needs, interests and potential of the individual, and create conditions for its comprehensive development and self-realization in the educational environment.

Conclusions. Today, tutoring is increasingly integrated into the system of traditional pedagogical practice, acting as an organic addition to it and at the same time an independent educational service that meets the new demands of the time. Its emergence and active development are due to the current challenges of modern society, dynamic changes in the economy, as well as transformations in the field of vocational training and employment.

Tutoring opens up the possibility of conscious construction of one's own educational path for students. Thanks to the support of a tutor, a student acquires the ability to independently determine individual educational goals, form a personal system of priorities, and build an internally motivated learning trajectory. In a changing and information-rich world, tutoring promotes conscious navigation in the streams of knowledge, helps to adapt to new requirements, and supports the development of critical thinking, reflection, and self-management skills. Thus, tutoring becomes not just a modern pedagogical function, but also a tool for adapting an individual to the conditions of a post-industrial society, in which the ability to learn throughout life (lifelong learning) becomes one of the key factors of success.

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